

Students' Perception of Teacher Education Program Accreditation in China

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RESEARCH ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Received: August 7, 2025 Reviewed: November 18, 2025 Accepted: November 26, 2025 Published: December 30, 2025</p> <p> Copyright © 2025 by the Author(s). This open-access article is distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.</p>	<p>China is carrying out the world's largest teacher education program accreditation project led by the Ministry of Education. While students are central stakeholders in this process, their perspectives have often been overlooked in traditional accreditation reviews. Addressing this gap, this study assessed the program compliance through student perceptions based on the three core dimensions of teacher education program accreditation framework proposed by the Chinese Ministry of Education in 2023. This study adopted a descriptive-inferential research design and statistical tools to test the research hypotheses. A researcher-made questionnaire was used to collect data from 200 students across four education majors at Zhangjiakou University, China. The results revealed that in terms of the three core dimensions, students highly rated the compliance of the majors with the teacher education program accreditation standards, but significant differences in assessments were found among students from different majors. This study confirms the value of systematically integrating student perceptions into teacher education program accreditation systems. It is recommended that future accreditation standards incorporate major-specific development indicators within the unified framework and that program administrators establish student assessment mechanisms during the self-evaluation phase. In addition, the findings of this study provide valuable insights for</p>

improving the quality of international teacher education, which is particularly relevant for countries that have implemented certification in teacher education programs.

Keywords: *students' perception, Teacher Education Program Accreditation, support conditions, quality assurance, student development*

Introduction

Teacher education program accreditation has become a hot topic in global teacher education research. China has established a systematic teacher education program accreditation system, characterized by government leadership, unified standards, and industry-education integration, which has become a benchmark model in global teacher education, providing a unique case for the international community to understand a centralized quality assurance approach that differs from decentralized Western certification systems (Zhao et al., 2022). While this nationally unified, mandatory accreditation model offers significant advantages in efficiency and standardization, it also raises a critical question: in the pursuit of standardization, have the diverse experiences and perceptions of students—as core stakeholders—based on their different major attributes, received sufficient attention? Based on the report from the Ministry of Education of China, 2,556 programs nationwide have passed the education program certification as of 2025. Therefore, summarizing China's experience with teacher education program accreditation offers valuable insights for improving the internationalization of teacher education (Zhu, 2020). The practical experience and findings from its large-scale implementation can provide key references for countries such as the United States, which implement limited-scale teacher education certification, in considering how to balance standard uniformity with program characteristics.

However, teacher education programs share commonalities with other accreditation mechanisms in terms of evaluation perspectives, as both rely on expert review methods (Ou & Luo, 2024). Taking into account the three most cited articles since 2018 in China's largest academic digital resource, the study of Hu (2018) focused on the significance and path of teacher education reform within the context of teacher education program accreditation. On the other hand, Zhang et al. (2018) focused on the development of teacher education programs in universities within the context of teacher education program accreditation, while Dong et al. (2022) studied the practice of ideological and political education in Chinese-style courses within the context of teachers' education program accreditation. Analysis of these current research reveals that while Chinese scholars have conducted extensive research on teacher education program accreditation, the majority of these researchers are faculty and experts in their field. There is a lack of research evaluating the outcomes of teacher education program development from the perspective of students. However, students are both the subjects and key participants in program development, and their experiences and evaluations of this development should be a key focus of scholarly research. However, the perception and evaluation of the implementation effect and practical influence of the accreditation program by students are rarely involved in the existing research.

Therefore, this study is grounded in the teacher education program accreditation framework established by the Chinese Ministry of Education and innovatively adopts

students' perspectives to systematically evaluate the practical effectiveness of teacher education program accreditation. This study expands the “results” evaluation dimension of the CIPP model by introducing the “user dimension”, which shifts the traditional effect measurement to the results evaluation with students' perception as the core. Students assessed three core indicators proposed by China's Ministry of Education: support conditions, quality assurance, and student development.

Therefore, the objectives were to systematically assess the students' perceptions of the effectiveness of teacher education programs and to explore whether there are significant differences in evaluation results among students with different major backgrounds. In addition, through the evaluation from the perspectives of the students with different major attributes, the effectiveness of the unified accreditation standard could be systematically described, providing municipal evidence for improving China's teachers education program accreditation policies and implementation paths, and offering unique evidence for large-scale practice of China's research on “stakeholder participation” and “results” evaluation in global teacher education program accreditation theory.

Methods

Research Design

This study is based on the standard framework of Teacher Education Program Accreditation of China, proposed by China's Ministry of Education (2023), and adopted a descriptive-inferential research design. The descriptive aspect was used to gather the perception of the student-respondents' assessment on the compliance of the majors with the teacher education program accreditation through statistical measures like mean and standard deviation, while the inferential component analyzed whether significant differences existed in the assessment of the respondents across majors in the three (3) accreditation areas surveyed.

Respondents

The respondents in this study were students from four (4) normal majors at Zhangjiakou University in China, namely: Chinese Language and Literature, Primary Education, Preschool Education, and Physical Education, with a total of 200 students—fifty (50) from each teacher education major. This was done to ensure the equal representation of student-respondents in all teacher education majors. Moreover, the student sample was determined using a cross-source random sampling technique, wherein students were randomly selected from multiple groups to ensure that the sample represented diverse sources within the population.

Research Instruments

A researcher-developed questionnaire was used to assess the compliance of the programs (majors) on the teacher education program accreditation across three (3) dimensions: support conditions, quality assurance, and student development, as proposed by China's Ministry of Education (2023), which are translated into actionable evaluation metrics. The instruments were content-validated by four (4) teacher education accreditation experts. Items were carefully checked to ensure that the items in the instrument accurately and adequately measure the three (3) constructs or dimensions of the teacher education program accreditation. The comments and suggestions of the experts were considered in the revision of the questionnaire. The edited version of the questionnaire was pilot tested to 40 students from four different

majors. The results demonstrated excellent internal consistency, yielding a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of .97. The five-point Likert scale, ranging from “strongly disagree” to “strongly agree,” was used to measure respondents’ agreement with the specified items. The scale scores were interpreted using the following criteria:

- 1.00–1.80 = Strongly Disagree/Non-Compliance
- 1.81–2.40 = Disagree/Low Compliance
- 2.41–3.40 = Neutral/Moderate Compliance
- 3.41–4.20 = Agree/High Compliance
- 4.21–5.00 = Strongly Agree/Excellent Compliance

Data Collection Procedure

To ensure the smooth implementation of the questionnaire survey, the researchers first obtained permission from the administrators of Zhangjiakou University, China. The data was collected during the 2024-2025 academic year at the university, with all questionnaires administered anonymously online to ensure data security. After completing the data collection, completeness and consistency checks were performed on the collected data to eliminate invalid responses before submitting it to the statistician for analysis. Subsequently, the analysis and interpretation of the data followed.

Analysis of Data

The collected research data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, including the mean and standard deviation, and the results were interpreted and supported by relevant literature and prior studies. Likewise, this study employed the Kruskal-Wallis H test to analyze assessment differences among four majors (Chinese Language and Literature, Primary Education, Preschool Education, and Physical Education) across three dimensions of teacher education program accreditation: support conditions, quality assurance, and student development. For dimensions showing significant differences, the Dunn's post hoc test with Bonferroni correction was applied to identify specific major groups with distinct characteristics. The effect size was measured using the epsilon squared (ϵ^2) statistic.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations were strictly observed in the conduct of this study. Prior to the administration of the questionnaire survey, permission was formally obtained from the administrators of Zhangjiakou University, China, to ensure the smooth and authorized implementation of the research. The respondents’ informed consent was also sought before their participation. They were properly oriented on the objectives, scope, and significance of the study, and were informed that their participation was voluntary. Furthermore, the respondents were assured of anonymity and confidentiality, and all information gathered was used solely for academic and research purposes.

Results and Discussion

As shown on Table 1, this study involved a total of 200 student respondents from four teacher education majors. The sample was distributed equally across these four majors, with each program (Chinese Language, Primary Education, Preschool Education, and Physical Education) contributing 50 students, constituting 25% of the total respondents, respectively. This balanced representation ensures that each major

perspective is accorded equal weight in the subsequent comparative analysis of student perceptions.

Table 1. Frequency Distribution of Student Respondents in Terms of Major

Major	Frequency	Percent
Chinese Language	50	25.0%
Primary Education	50	25.0%
Preschool Education	50	25.0%
Physical Education	50	25.0%
Total	200	100%

It can be gleaned from Table 2.1 that, in terms of support conditions, all five items received high ratings. The results suggest that students perceived excellent compliance of the four teacher education majors in terms of support conditions. This means that students were able to experience the achievements in supporting conditions of teacher education programs, driven by teacher education program accreditation.

Table 2.1. Perception of the Student-Respondents on the Compliance of the Major with the Teacher Education Program Accreditation in Terms of Support Condition

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1 A vocational skills training platform has been established.	4.24	0.60	Excellent Compliance
2 There is a mechanism for the management, maintenance, renewal, and sharing of education and teaching facilities.	4.27	0.53	Excellent Compliance
3 Teaching resources meet the needs of student training.	4.26	0.58	Excellent Compliance
4 The major has a primary school or preschool textbook resource database.	4.24	0.62	Excellent Compliance
5 The major has a database of excellent primary schools or educational teaching cases.	4.24	0.63	Excellent Compliance
Overall - Support Conditions	4.25	0.59	Excellent Compliance

Legend: 1.00-1.80=SD/NC, 1.81-2.40=D/LC 2.41-3.40=N/MC, 3.41-4.20=A/HC, 4.21-5.00=SA/EC

Among the five items rated, Item 2, which focuses on a mechanism for management, maintenance, renewal, and sharing of education and teaching facilities, recorded the highest mean score (M = 4.27) and the lowest standard deviation (SD = 0.53). This indicates that students have the highest assessment and the most consistent agreement on the effectiveness of this mechanism. In contrast, Item 5, which is about database of excellent primary schools or educational teaching, received the lowest mean score (M = 4.24) with the largest standard deviation of (SD = 0.63). Students' highest ratings for support conditions, especially for the mechanism of education and teaching facilities, profoundly reflect the strong driving role played by China's teacher education program accreditation as a state-led mandatory system. As an authoritative resource

allocation framework, the teacher education program accreditation standards effectively guide fiscal and school funds at all levels to prioritize visible and easily assessable hardware areas such as facility construction (Bo & Zhang, 2025). This resource investment, strongly driven by state power, has yielded significant and easily perceptible results among students, thereby earning highly consistent evaluations.

However, the development of a database of excellent primary schools or educational teaching cases as a new accreditation metric has encountered implementation challenges. To better understand this discrepancy, the study referenced field reports from 16 Ministry of Education experts as key triangulation evidence. The reports repeatedly highlighted systemic issues in software support for case repository development, despite substantial hardware investments driven by accreditation requirements. The relatively low scores and significant disagreements align with findings across multiple disciplines, including “low utilization rates of primary school teaching resource libraries and exemplary case repositories” and “insufficient promotion and lack of incentive mechanisms.”

This phenomenon can be explained through the “institutional homology” theory, which posits that organizations conform to authoritative systems to gain external legitimacy. While universities’ increased investments in teaching facilities under accreditation metrics demonstrate forced compliance, the development of soft resources requiring endogenous innovation—such as case repositories—lags significantly behind. Existing research confirms this. Cong (2025) explicitly noted that current university evaluations remain reactive, lacking proactive improvement mechanisms based on institutional development needs, resulting in a “hardware-heavy, software-light” approach. This reveals a disconnect between institutional “proactivity” and “implementation capacity” under strong national strategic impetus, underscoring the need for future policies to shift from external pressure to building internal momentum, guiding institutions to transition from passive compliance to proactive improvement.

Table 2.2. Perception of the Student-Respondents on the Compliance of the Major with the Teacher Education Program Accreditation in Terms of Quality Assurance

	Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1	There is a quality assurance system in the university.	4.27	0.54	Excellent Compliance
2	There are clear quality requirements for each major teaching link (including core courses, internships, graduation theses, etc.).	4.28	0.54	Excellent Compliance
3	There is a regular monitoring mechanism for the quality of the teaching process.	4.26	0.53	Excellent Compliance
4	Regularly monitor and evaluate the quality of all major teaching links to ensure the achievement of graduation requirements.	4.29	0.54	Excellent Compliance
5	There is a graduate tracking and feedback mechanism.	4.23	0.59	Excellent Compliance
	Overall - Quality Assurance	4.26	0.55	Excellent Compliance

Legend: 1.00-1.80=SD/NC, 1.81-2.40=D/LC 2.41-3.40=N/MC, 3.41-4.20=A/HC, 4.21-5.00=SA/EC

As shown in Table 2.2, all five items achieved high scores in quality assurance. The findings indicate that students perceived excellent compliance of the four teacher education majors in terms of quality assurance. This demonstrates how students can tangibly experience the tangible outcomes of quality assurance initiatives driven by teachers' education program accreditation.

Among the five items, the indicator (Item 4) on regular monitoring and evaluation of quality of all major teaching for the achievement of graduation requirements received the highest mean of 4.29 (SD = 0.54). This result indicates that students perceived this mechanism as the most effective and demonstrated the strongest consensus in their ratings. In contrast, the item (Indicator 5) related to graduate tracking and feedback mechanism received the lowest average score of 4.23, along with a considerably higher standard deviation of 0.59.

The students' high rating of regularly monitoring and evaluating the quality of all major teaching links can be explained by their implementation features and institutional context. Schools regularly monitor these components through course evaluations, practical assessments, and thesis reviews, with clear implementation pathways, simple methods, controllable costs, and short feedback cycles, thus achieving high implementation effectiveness (Fen et al., 2020). This finding aligns with the Ministry of Education's expert report during the onsite inspections, which noted that *"a quality monitoring framework for key teaching components has been established at the school level,"* demonstrating the effectiveness of the quality control mechanism for these components.

However, the graduate tracking and feedback mechanism, as a long-term feedback component in the quality assurance system, finds its low ratings strongly corroborated by the in-depth diagnoses from expert reports. Sixteen experts unanimously pointed out in multidisciplinary feedback that the university's graduate tracking feedback mechanism is *"incomplete, lacks a continuous improvement mechanism, and the third-party evaluation system introduced fails to effectively align with accreditation standards."* This triangulation approach confirms the scientific validity of students' perceived implementation difficulties, revealing systemic weaknesses in institutional design, resource allocation, and closed-loop improvements.

The mechanism's characteristics of cross-regional operation, extended duration, and high costs, combined with the lack of sustained improvement motivation, have collectively resulted in a significant gap between compliance appearances and substantive outcomes. This conclusion is supported by evidence from prior studies by Zhong et al. (2022), who identified challenges and institutional flaws in graduate tracking and feedback.

Moreover, Xu (2020) and Li (2021) also highlighted through case studies of local universities that current employment tracking systems still exhibit significant shortcomings in data integration and feedback improvement. This comparison exposes deeper challenges in quality assurance system construction under teacher education accreditation: internal monitoring mechanisms that are easy to implement and yield short-term visible results tend to gain more recognition, while external feedback and improvement mechanisms requiring multiparty collaboration and long-term investment often face implementation difficulties.

Table 2.3. Perception of the Student-Respondents on the Compliance of the Major with the Teacher Education Program Accreditation in Terms of Student Development

Indicators	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1 There are effective institutional measures to attract students who are willing to teach and have good quality.	4.27	0.58	Excellent Compliance
2 The major understands students' development demands and strengthens learning situation analysis	4.27	0.59	Excellent Compliance
3 There is a teaching management system that takes into account both common requirements and individual needs.	4.26	0.59	Excellent Compliance
4 The major can provide students with multi-dimensional guidance in a timely manner.	4.24	0.64	Excellent Compliance
5 It can monitor the learning progress of normal school students and ensure that they meet the graduation requirements upon graduation.	4.29	0.55	Excellent Compliance
Overall - Student Development	4.26	0.59	Excellent Compliance

Legend: 1.00-1.80=SD/NC, 1.81-2.40=D/LC 2.41-3.40=N/MC, 3.41-4.20=A/HC, 4.21-5.00=SA/EC

As shown in Table 2.3, all five items received high ratings. The findings indicate that students perceived excellent compliance of the four teacher education majors in terms of student development. Among the items, Item 5, which focuses on monitoring of the learning progress of normal school students to meet the graduation requirements upon graduation, received the highest scores ($M = 4.29$, $SD = 0.55$). These ratings reflect strong student consensus regarding the effectiveness of measures taken to ensure compliance with graduation requirements. In contrast, Item 4, which deals with multidimensional guidance on time, obtained the lowest mean score ($M = 4.24$) along with the highest standard deviation ($SD = 0.64$), suggesting comparatively varied perceptions among respondents.

The high recognition students have for the graduation requirement achievement mechanism profoundly reflects the significant effectiveness of China's teacher education program accreditation as a state-led mandatory system in evaluating graduation outcomes. The long-standing "strict admission and strict graduation" framework in China's undergraduate education has prompted universities to develop a quality management logic centered on "ensuring graduation" (Wang, 2019).

Under China's institutional context, various programs often prioritize ensuring students' smooth graduation as their primary task to demonstrate program quality. To this end, programs establish a series of process monitoring mechanisms, including regular academic evaluations, learning progress tracking, and academic early warning systems, to ensure students meet graduation requirements. This practice has been extensively discussed in relevant research. In fact, Zhang (2022), through textual analysis of six applied undergraduate institutions, proposed a systematic strategy for building an academic early warning system for local applied undergraduate institutions. Xiong (2023) also developed an academic early warning and support model that

integrates multi-source data from student records, shifting focus from outcome assessment to process monitoring.

The confirmation by Ministry of Education experts in their on-campus inspection reported that “*academic early warning mechanisms have been established at the institutional level*”, thereby aligning effectively with students’ positive evaluations and collectively highlighting the successful practice of the accreditation system in ensuring the quality of educational outputs.

In contrast, the divergent student evaluations of academic mentoring services clearly revealed significant shortcomings in the current accreditation system regarding process evaluation and support mechanisms. Student assessments of mentoring essentially constitute formative evaluations, focusing on comprehensiveness and timeliness, with students believing service programs should cover multiple domains.

On the other hand, this evaluation emphasized process quality of mentoring services (Han & Wei, 2024); while Aquino and Cabrera (2021) noted that student evaluations are indeed used in institutional assessments to evaluate complex service systems encompassing admissions, mentorship, cultural integration, and logistical support, highlighting the comprehensiveness of their evaluation framework. As previously mentioned, student satisfaction with “meeting graduation requirements” falls under outcome-oriented assessment. While they express satisfaction with this key indicator of personal development, they simultaneously demand higher-quality services during the mentoring process. This indicates that contemporary teacher candidates not only focus on achieving learning outcomes but also expect substantial and meaningful learning experiences.

This finding corroborates the research conclusions of Acoba and Ariola (2025) that process factors such as classroom learning environments show significant positive correlations with student academic performance. This also presents a critical challenge for teacher education program accreditation standards. The issues highlighted in expert reports, such as “insufficiently in-depth personalized mentoring” and “insufficient mentoring frequency,” form a triangular corroboration with students’ low ratings, collectively revealing inadequate institutional provisions in process support mechanisms within the accreditation system. The results also show that the teacher education accreditation has achieved remarkable results in promoting the construction of the result-oriented evaluation system, but it still needs to strengthen the construction of the process support and evaluation mechanism.

As shown in Table 3, the Kruskal-Wallis test reveals significant differences across three dimensions of the four majors. A significant difference was found in the perception of support conditions among the four majors ($H(3) = 73.38, p < .001, \epsilon^2 = 0.37$), indicating a large effect size. Descriptive statistics show that the median scores of Preschool Education (Mdn = 4.6, IQR = 1.0) and Physical Education (Mdn = 5.0, IQR = 1.0) were higher than those of Chinese Language and Literature (Mdn = 4.0, IQR = 0.4) and Primary Education (Mdn = 4.0, IQR = 0.0). To clarify the specific pattern of differences, Dunn's post-hoc test with Bonferroni correction confirmed that scores for Preschool Education and Physical Education were significantly higher than those in Chinese Language and Literature and Primary Education (all comparisons $p < .001$).

Notably, the comparison between Chinese Language and Literature and Primary Education ($p = .130$) and between Preschool Education and Physical Education ($p = 1.000$) indicated that students from different majors essentially formed two distinct groups. Analysis results in the quality assurance dimension and student development dimension further validated the stability of this grouping pattern. Specifically, these

differences suggest that students' perceptions of program compliance with accreditation standards are systematically influenced by their specific majors.

Table 3. Group Differences in Assessment of Student-Respondents on Teacher Education Program Accreditation in Terms of Three Elements (Major as Test Factor)

Dimension	Major	Mdn	IQR	Kruskal-Wallis Test	Post-hoc Comparison (Dunn's test with Bonferroni correction)
Support Conditions	Chinese Language and Literature	4.0	0.4	H(3) = 73.38, p < .001, $\epsilon^2 = 0.37$	Preschool, Physical > Chinese, Primary (all p<.001)
	Primary Education	4.0	0.0		Chinese = Primary (p=.130)
	Preschool Education	4.6	1.0		Preschool = Physical (p=1.000)
	Physical Education	5.0	1.0		
Quality Assurance	Chinese Language and Literature	4.0	0.0	H(3) =55.46, p < .001, $\epsilon^2 = 0.28$	Preschool, Physical > Chinese, Primary (all p<.001)
	Primary Education	4.0	0.0		Chinese = Primary (p=1.000)
	Preschool Education	4.7	1.0		Preschool = Physical (p=1.000)
	Physical Education	5.0	1.0		
Student Development	Chinese Language and Literature	4.0	0.0	H(3) = 59.12, p < .001, $\epsilon^2 = 0.30$	Preschool, Physical > Chinese, Primary (all p<.001)
	Primary Education	4.0	0.0		Chinese = Primary (p=.286)
	Preschool Education	4.8	1.0		Preschool = Physical (p=1.000)
	Physical Education	5.0	1.0		

The research findings confirm a fundamental reality: students from different disciplines exhibit significant disparities in their perceptions of teacher education accreditation compliance. This demonstrates that in the practice and evaluation of teacher education accreditation, all programs should not be treated as a homogeneous entity. Traditional accreditation standards based on undifferentiated criteria may obscure the uneven development across disciplines, potentially leading to imbalanced resource allocation and misguided strategies. Existing studies have corroborated this observation. Xu and Zhang (2025) found that accreditation metrics lack flexibility in practice, making it difficult to meet the diverse developmental needs of teacher-training programs across different types of universities and student demographics. Studies by She and Du (2025) and Li (2025) highlighted the limitations of current standardized evaluation models, and the uniform certification criteria force diverse schools and disciplines to adopt identical talent development approaches, which stifles the

distinctive growth of teacher-training programs. This creates a conflict between accreditation requirements and program-specific development, ultimately leading to homogenization in academic program construction. Therefore, the accreditation system has a positive effect on the development of normal education, but the imbalance of the development of the major should be paid attention to in the process of its implementation.

Furthermore, the results provide enlightenment for understanding the reasons for the evaluation of the differences in the majors. The lack of difference in the high evaluation of pre-school education-physical education and the lack of difference in the low evaluation of Chinese language and literature-primary education are all due to the common attributes of the majors in the group. This difference shows that the teacher education program accreditation of normal education majors does not promote the overall quality of all majors, but the uneven quality of major development outcomes. Both physical education and preschool education are classified as “practice-oriented” majors, characterized by concentrated resource allocation and well-aligned evaluation criteria.

In contrast, Chinese Language and Literature and Primary Education share the common trait of being “humanities-oriented” majors that rely on long-term accumulation and emphasize substantive development, and the accreditation indicators are difficult to effectively capture the core dimensions of quality improvement in these majors (Bo & Zhang, 2025). This finding is strongly supported by the triangulation verification of the Ministry of Education experts’ on-site inspection reports. The experts explicitly noted that physical education programs receive prioritized funding and facility support, while majors like Chinese Language and Literature face challenges with inadequate resource allocation mechanisms. This pattern of differentiated resource distribution aligns closely with the study's findings: “practice-oriented” programs (preschool education, physical education) consistently scored higher than “humanities-oriented” programs (Chinese literature, primary education). Existing research, examining multiple dimensions including major hierarchy, curriculum design, internship assessments, student satisfaction, and institutional implementation, revealed that major attributes significantly influence the effectiveness of teacher education program accreditation.

In addition, Chen’s (2025) research demonstrates that the major orientation directly influences students’ perception and satisfaction with teaching practices under the accreditation framework, thereby affecting the realization of accreditation outcomes. Shao et al. (2025) also argued that major hierarchy and attributes significantly influence accreditation priorities and evaluation criteria, further supporting the notion that professional attributes determine accreditation effectiveness. Wu and Zhu (2025) further highlighted that universities with distinct major profiles encounter varying institutional adaptation challenges in accreditation implementation. This finding establishes the key position of the major attribute in the effect of teacher education program accreditation, and suggests that the problem of unbalanced major development can be solved by classifying the major attribute and adopting different major development measures according to the category.

Conclusion and Future Works

To improve the quality of teacher education, China's teacher education program accreditation has become a key institutional tool. This study, through an innovative adoption of a student evaluation perspective, found that students generally provided

excellent assessment on their program compliance, which validates the effectiveness of the unified standards of teacher education program accreditation in meeting students' basic expectations and establishing quality baselines. However, the assessment differences among programs in dimensions such as support conditions, quality assurance, and student development reveal a deeper challenge in the implementation of accreditation: how to address common issues across programs while also meeting the developmental needs of programs with different attributes under unified standards.

This discovery provides important insights for the Chinese Ministry of Education to improve the implementation standards and processes of teacher education program accreditation. For China's teacher education program accreditation system, this study suggests that the Chinese Ministry of Education could explore the establishment of an implementation mechanism with "unified standards and categorized pathways." Specifically, within a unified accreditation framework, a major development framework may be added. In self-assessment, evidence presentation, and expert evaluation, indicators for characteristic development based on the major attribute may be set across all dimensions of the accreditation standards, such as support conditions, quality assurance, and student development.

Moreover, these indicators can be categorized into guiding development metrics for different types of programs, allowing each program to substantiate its development achievements based on its specific category. These metrics will serve as key reference indicators for assessing the compliance of programs with teacher education accreditation standards. By establishing these major development indicators across all dimensions, programs can be guided to flexibly adapt to teacher education program accreditation standards from their own major attributes, avoiding homogenized development and achieving distinctive teacher education pathways.

At the institutional operational level, administrators could also attach great importance to the significant role of student evaluation and establish a regular student assessment feedback mechanism. This study finds that the pain points and difficulties in teacher education program accreditation are precisely the issues reflected in slightly low student assessments. For example, the construction of primary school teaching case libraries based on new standards, the implementation difficulties of graduate tracking feedback mechanisms, and the long-term "strict entry, lenient exit" policy in China, which leads to overemphasizing graduation outcomes while neglecting the guidance process, have all become factors contributing to low student satisfaction. The research demonstrates that student evaluations are scientifically valid and hold strong reference value for major participation in teacher education program accreditation.

Essentially, China's teacher education program accreditation follows a six-year cycle, during which there is a phase of major self-evaluation. This study suggests that major administrators may organize student evaluations during the self-evaluation phase based on accreditation standards, identify weak points in program development, and take corrective measures to improve compliance with accreditation standards, thereby enhancing the final evaluation scores by experts from the Ministry of Education.

This study provides a clear path for subsequent research, but it also has limitations. First, the sample is sourced from a single institution, which ensures internal consistency in interdisciplinary comparisons but limits the applicability of conclusions to different types of teacher-training colleges. Second, the research primarily employs quantitative data, revealing differences in student evaluations across majors but did not delve into the specific causes and mechanisms behind these factors. Finally, this study is a cross-sectional design, reflecting only a static state at a certain point in the

accreditation cycle. However, the accreditation of teacher-training programs in China is a cyclical process, and this study could not track the long-term dynamic impacts of accreditation on program development. Future research could expand the sample scope, adopt mixed methods, and conduct longitudinal tracking to deepen the understanding of the impacts of teacher education program accreditation in China and to test the scientific validity of the student evaluation perspective.

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Conflict of Interest

The author declares that there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) Declaration Statement

When preparing manuscripts, authors use AI tools to perform basic grammar and spelling checks, and then they edit the content as needed.